

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF AORTIC PARAMETERS IN HEALTHY AND SICK CHILDREN WITH VARIOUS HEART DEFECTS AT THE AGE OF 3 YEARS

Khamidova Nigora Karimboevna¹

Baymuradov Ravshan Radjabovich²

¹ Basic doctoral student of the Department of Anatomy and Clinics of Anatomy (OHTA), Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

² Head of the Department of Anatomy and Clinics of Anatomy (OHTA), Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10032549>

Summary

A study of the size of the aorta and its parts in sick children with heart defects 3 years old in comparison with data from healthy children of the same age showed that not all studied indicators changed significantly in relation to the data from healthy children.

Key words: congenital heart defects, aortic parameters.

Relevance. CHD, the most common type of birth defect, is characterized by congenital malformations of the heart walls, valves, or blood vessels that can be divided into several phenotypes, including atrial septal defect, ventricular septal defect (VSD), atrioventricular septal defect, tetralogy of Fallot (TOF), and syndrome hypoplasia of the left heart [1]. CHD affects $\approx 1\%$ of live births and is responsible for 30% of fetal deaths [2]. Due to the high morbidity and mortality rates, extensive research has been conducted to identify the causes of congenital heart defects; however, the causes of most cases remain elusive. Moreover, the parameters of cardiac components have not been studied, and the available information is contradictory [3-5].

Materials and methods: 40 3-year-old boys, healthy and with discernible heart defects, were studied. The study involved children of a preschool institution in the city of Bukhara who underwent echocardiography examinations at the Nasriddin Shams clinic in the Bukhara region of Uzbekistan.

Results of the study: The results obtained showed that in healthy 3-year-old boys, the diameter of the aorta was on average 16.00 ± 0.34 mm, and the ascending part of the aorta was on average slightly smaller than the previous one, amounting to 14.35 ± 0.32 mm, further, all the described dimensions were carried in a descending order, averaging a diameter of the aortic arch of 12.20 ± 0.31 mm, of the descending part of the aorta of 10.30 ± 0.28 mm, and of the abdominal aorta of 8.50 ± 0.26 mm. We accepted these dimensions of the aorta of healthy 3-year-old children as a standard indicator for this region and used

them for a comparative assessment of the parameters of children with heart defects.

Analysis of the results of these sick 3-year-old children showed that the aortic diameter was 16.85 ± 0.32 mm. This parameter is 5.31% greater than in healthy children of the same age; in addition, the data were significantly different from each other ($P < 0.05$). Almost the same result was obtained when studying the size of the ascending aorta, the size of which was 15.05 ± 0.31 mm, which is 4.88% more than in healthy children, and in this case the result was significantly different from the data of healthy children ($P < 0.05$). In terms of the size of the aortic arch, significantly different results were obtained in sick children, where this parameter (12.85 ± 0.31 mm) was significantly larger ($P < 0.05$) than in healthy children - 12.20 ± 0.31 mm.

Conclusion: Thus, the study of the size of the aorta and its parts in sick children with heart defects 3 years old in comparison with data from healthy children of the same age showed that of the 5 parameters studied, 3 changed significantly, 2 parameters did not differ significantly in relation to data from healthy children. The diameters of the aorta, ascending aorta and abdominal aorta were significantly different. It has been established that heart defects negatively affect not only the anthropometric parameters of 3-year-old children, but also the diameters of the aorta, ascending and descending aorta, aortic arch and the diameter of the abdominal aorta.

References:

1. Wolf M, Basson CT. The molecular genetics of congenital heart disease: a review of recent developments. *Curr Opin Cardiol*. 2010;25:192–197. doi: 10.1097/HCO.0b013e328337b4ce.
2. Hoffman J. The global burden of congenital heart disease. *Cardiovasc J Afr*. 2013;24:141–145. doi: 10.5830/CVJA-2013-028.
3. Хамидова Н.К. Тешаев Ш.Ж., Сравнительная характеристика антропометрических параметров детей с различными пороками сердца // Самарканд Проблемы биологии и медицины, 2019. №4/2, (115). – С. 255-257.
4. Хамидова Н.К., Тешаев Ш.Ж. Турли юрак нуқсонлари бўлган болалар жисмоний ўсиш кўрсаткичларининг морфометрик таснифи // Журнал. Тиббиётда янги кун. 2020, № 2/1(30/1) С. 54-57.
5. Ш. М. Камалова, ШЖ Тешаев, НК Хамидова. Параметры физического развития 8-летних детей в норме и при сколиозе. // Журнал. Морфология. 2020, -С. 92-93.

